

Human Detection of AI-Generated Phishing: Study Protocol and Dataset Design for the Threat Terminal Experiment

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Abstract

Much of the historically evaluated anti-phishing guidance and many training approaches have emphasized surface-level cues such as grammar, sender inconsistencies, and urgency as primary detection heuristics, and the empirical research base has largely relied on historically authored stimuli that often contained visible linguistic flaws. AI-generated phishing is changing that landscape: grammatically fluent, contextually plausible phishing is now possible at low marginal cost, yet the research base has been slower to adapt. This paper presents the study protocol, dataset design, and methodological framework for an experiment examining which phishing techniques produce the lowest human detection rates when all stimuli are AI-generated to partially standardize linguistic quality across conditions. Data is collected through Threat Terminal, a purpose-built game-based research platform where participants classify AI-generated emails as phishing or legitimate, express confidence in each decision, and receive forensic signal breakdowns after each session. The dataset comprises 1,000 cards across six phishing technique categories and three legitimate email categories, all generated by large language models to partially standardize writing quality across conditions. Hypotheses are stated prior to full analysis to distinguish predictions from post-hoc rationalizations. Initial pilot data from 70 participants and 996 classified cards are included to confirm platform viability and data collection quality. This paper is a study protocol and dataset design document; empirical findings will be reported in a separate publication upon reaching the target participant sample.

Keywords: phishing detection, social engineering, AI-generated content, security awareness training, human factors, game-based research

1. Introduction

Phishing remains one of the most common initial access vectors in enterprise security breaches, accounting for 16% of confirmed breaches in the most recent Verizon Data Breach Investigations Report (Verizon, 2025) and figuring prominently in the 60% of breaches involving a human element. Security awareness training has long addressed this threat through a variety of approaches. Among the programs that have been studied empirically, surface-level signal recognition has been one recurring component. Dhamija,

Tygar, and Hearst (2006) found that users relied heavily on visual and contextual cues when distinguishing legitimate from fraudulent content and often failed to use available security indicators. Jampen, Gür, Sutter, and Tellenbach (2020) reviewed a range of anti-phishing training approaches and found that heuristic-based detection (recognizing cues such as grammatical errors, sender inconsistencies, and urgency) was a common emphasis across the programs they evaluated, alongside other training strategies. These heuristics had practical value when many phishing campaigns contained visible linguistic artifacts, as was often the case when campaigns were authored by non-native speakers working at volume.

The reliability of these surface-level cues as detection signals is now under growing pressure. Large language model (LLM) technology has made it possible to generate grammatically fluent, contextually plausible phishing at low marginal cost. AI-generated phishing emails have proven comparably effective to professionally authored campaigns in organizational settings (Bethany et al., 2025) and can achieve click-through rates on par with human-crafted spear phishing (Heiding et al., 2024). These developments suggest that some traditional detection signals may be less reliable than they once were for discriminating phishing from legitimate email.

Current security awareness training may not yet have fully adapted to this shift. The programs evaluated by Jampen et al. (2020) predominantly emphasized heuristic-based detection methods developed for an earlier generation of phishing attacks. The empirical research base on human phishing susceptibility, while substantial, largely predates the AI writing transition and measures responses to stimuli that would now be considered easy to detect.

This leaves a gap in the evidence base: practitioners and researchers do not yet have reliable empirical data on which phishing techniques bypass trained humans when all stimuli are AI-generated and writing quality is no longer a distinguishing cue. The question is not which emails look bad, but which structural and contextual properties of a phishing attempt are most cognitively difficult to detect when the writing cannot serve as a signal.

This paper presents the study protocol and dataset design for an experiment designed to answer that question. The study uses Threat Terminal, a purpose-built game-based research platform where participants classify AI-generated emails, express confidence in each classification, and receive detailed forensic signal breakdowns after each session. All stimuli, both phishing and legitimate, are AI-generated using two Claude model versions, so that writing quality is consistent across the dataset. Model provenance is recorded for each card to permit post-hoc analysis of any residual quality differences between generators. Participants classify using both message content and forensic metadata (email authentication headers, URL characteristics, reply-to analysis), so detection is not based on linguistic content alone. The primary independent variable is phishing technique category; difficulty tier serves as a secondary independent variable that varies both the density of content-level signals and the forensic metadata profile (e.g., authentication status) across cards.

This paper makes the following contributions:

1. A detailed study protocol for an experiment on human phishing detection across six technique categories under AI-quality conditions
2. A structured 1,000-card dataset design with four difficulty tiers per technique and structured representation of legitimate email categories
3. A game-based data collection platform that enables high-quality research participation at scale outside laboratory settings
4. Hypotheses stated prior to full analysis, distinguishing predictions from post-hoc rationalization
5. Initial pilot data from 70 participants and 996 classified cards confirming platform viability and data collection quality

The full empirical findings paper, including bypass rates by technique, group comparisons, and confidence-accuracy analysis, will be submitted upon reaching the target participant sample. Publishing the protocol before full analysis separates study design from eventual findings and reduces post-hoc interpretation risk.

2. Background and Related Work

2.1 Human Susceptibility to Phishing

Research on human phishing susceptibility has produced consistent findings over two decades. Downs, Holbrook, and Cranor (2006) found that susceptibility correlates with inattention to contextual cues and reliance on surface-level legitimacy signals. Vishwanath et al. (2011) demonstrated that habitual information processing, rather than deliberate analysis, accounts for a significant proportion of phishing victimization. Workman (2008) examined pretext and social engineering mechanisms, finding that authority cues and social proof systematically lower resistance to phishing attempts. Parsons, Butavicius, Delfabbro, and Lillie (2019) extended this line of work with 985 participants and found that susceptibility varied by social influence principle: phishing emails employing consistency and reciprocity were most successful, while those using scarcity and social proof were least successful, suggesting that technique-level analysis is essential to understanding phishing risk. Greene, Steves, Theofanos, and Kostick (2018) demonstrated in an ecologically valid workplace study over 4.5 years that user context at the moment of email receipt is a significant explanatory variable, finding that when the phishing premise aligns with the recipient's current work context, click rates increase substantially regardless of training history.

Kumaraguru et al. (2009) evaluated embedded anti-phishing training with 515 participants and found that training improved detection, that a second reinforcement message further reduced susceptibility, and that users retained knowledge after 28 days. However, Caputo et al. (2014) found that scaling embedded training to an organizational setting was substantially more difficult: many employees left the training page before reading the material, and framing had no significant effect on subsequent click rates. As the authors concluded, “making embedded training effective in a corporate setting is more difficult than earlier studies suggest.” Lain, Kostianen, and Capkun (2022) conducted a large-scale organizational phishing study with over 14,000 participants over 15 months and found that a small fraction of employees account for a disproportionate share of click-throughs, suggesting that aggregate susceptibility statistics obscure meaningful individual variation.

A consistent limitation across this literature is the quality of phishing stimuli used in studies. Most research uses historically authored phishing emails or researcher-generated templates. These stimuli vary substantially in linguistic quality, and recipients' detection performance is partially explained by writing quality rather than technique structure alone.

2.2 AI-Generated Phishing

The introduction of capable large language models has attracted research attention to AI-assisted phishing generation. Hazell (2023; preprint) demonstrated that LLMs can generate personalized spear phishing at scale with minimal expert input. Bethany et al. (2025) extended this line of work to a large university workforce of approximately 9,000 individuals and found that LLM-generated lateral phishing emails were as effective as those written by communications professionals. Heiding et al. (2024; preprint) conducted a controlled comparison across four conditions and found that fully AI-automated phishing achieved a 54% click-through rate, matching human expert performance and exceeding generic phishing by 350%.

An important implication of this body of work is that linguistic quality, historically one of the most commonly used surface-level detection signals, can no longer be assumed to discriminate phishing from legitimate correspondence. This study is designed specifically to measure detection performance in a world where that signal is unavailable.

2.3 Game-Based Research Methods in Security

Game-based data collection has been explored as a method for scaling security research outside laboratory settings. Kumaraguru et al. (2007) designed PhishGuru, an embedded training system that delivered phishing education at the moment of failure. Their follow-up study (Kumaraguru et al., 2009) evaluated the approach with 515 participants in the field and demonstrated that game-like embedded training produced measurable retention at 28 days. Sheng et al. (2007) extended this line of work with Anti-Phishing Phil, an interactive game in which players learned to identify phishing URLs by examining contextual cues; the game-based approach outperformed both tutorial-based and existing online training materials. More recently, Wen, Lin, Chen, and Andersen (2019) developed What.Hack, a role-playing phishing simulation game in which participants processed emails across progressively difficult levels, demonstrating that gamified training increased engagement and detection skill compared to standard training methods. The game-based approach in this study addresses two problems simultaneously: it provides a mechanism for recruiting participants at scale, and it creates an incentive structure (scoring, XP, progression) that maintains engagement across multiple classification sessions.

2.4 Gap in the Literature

Recent work has demonstrated that AI-generated phishing can match human-authored phishing in effectiveness and plausibility (Hazell, 2023; Bethany et al., 2025; Heiding et al., 2024), but this research focuses on generation capability and aggregate click-through rates rather than on technique-level detection. Existing phishing detection research has not yet addressed technique-level bypass rates under AI-quality conditions. Studies use historically authored stimuli that cannot isolate technique from quality as independent variables. The author has not identified published work that systematically compares human detection rates across phishing technique categories when all stimuli are AI-generated at consistent linguistic quality, based on a review of the phishing susceptibility, security awareness training, and AI-generated social engineering literatures cited in this paper. This absence motivated the present study, though the claim is bounded by the scope of that review rather than by a formal systematic search protocol. It is worth noting that equalizing linguistic quality could also cause technique-level bypass rates to converge, producing a finding of limited or no meaningful difference between categories. Such a result would itself be informative, suggesting that technique structure matters less than linguistic quality as a detection signal, and would carry its own implications for training design.

3. Research Questions

The study is organized around one primary research question and three secondary questions.

Primary Research Question: When all stimuli are AI-generated to partially standardize linguistic quality, which phishing techniques produce the lowest human detection rates?

Secondary Research Question 1: Does professional security background improve phishing detection uniformly across technique categories, or is the advantage concentrated in specific technique types?

Secondary Research Question 2: Does overconfidence correlate with specific phishing techniques? Do participants who misclassify emails tend to do so while expressing high confidence?

Secondary Research Question 3: Does detection accuracy differ meaningfully between information security professionals, technical non-security professionals, and general users?

4. Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formed prior to full data collection and are stated here to distinguish predictions from post-hoc rationalizations. A transparency note: initial pilot data from 70 participants was available during the drafting of this protocol, and the directional patterns in that pilot data are visible in Section 7.2. The hypotheses are grounded in the prior literature cited below rather than in pilot observations, but readers should be aware that complete isolation from preliminary data cannot be claimed. The hypotheses are consistent with established findings in the phishing susceptibility literature applied to an AI-generated stimulus environment.

H1: Technique-Level Bypass Rates

Among the five named technique categories, Pretexting will produce the highest bypass rate. Pretexting conceals malicious intent inside a plausible narrative; the request itself appears mundane, requiring detection of the surrounding setup rather than the content of the ask. Fluent Prose, which removes every conventional social engineering mechanism simultaneously (see Section 5.3), is expected to produce a high bypass rate as well, but serves a structurally distinct role as a baseline measuring detection failure when no identifiable trick is present. The empirically informative comparisons are therefore the relative ordering among the five named techniques and the gap between those techniques and the Fluent Prose baseline.

Credential Harvest is expected to produce the lowest bypass rate. It is the technique most consistently covered in security awareness training, and the structural fingerprint (an invitation to authenticate somewhere) is recognizable even when the prose is high quality.

H2: Group Differences

As an exploratory hypothesis, participants self-reporting as information security or cybersecurity professionals (INFOSEC group) are expected to demonstrate higher detection rates than technical non-security professionals and general users in aggregate. This hypothesis is exploratory because professional background is self-reported, optional, and unverified, and the resulting group sizes may be unbalanced. Wash (2020) found that IT experts follow a three-stage detection process (comprehension, suspicion, and investigation) and that their advantage derives primarily from recognizing inconsistencies between contextual cues rather than from identifying individual red flags. Dhamija, Tygar, and Hearst (2006) provided complementary evidence: in a controlled study, 23% of participants failed to use browser-based security indicators, and even sophisticated users were deceived by high-quality visual attacks, suggesting that detection skill depends on learned attentional strategies rather than general intelligence. Security professionals benefit from regular exposure to threat patterns, phishing simulations, and incident data. The more important secondary question is whether this advantage is uniform across technique categories or concentrated in techniques that require technical knowledge to detect.

H3: Confidence-Accuracy Mismatch

Participants will be overconfident when wrong. Canfield, Fischhoff, and Davis (2016) applied signal detection theory to phishing classification and found that participants' confidence did not reliably track their detection accuracy, leaving them vulnerable despite cautious behavior. Wang, Li, and Rao (2016) replicated this pattern: across 600 participants, confidence beliefs poorly predicted detection accuracy and poorly explained its variance, with dispositional optimism and familiarity increasing overconfidence. In a follow-up study, Canfield, Fischhoff, and Davis (2019) measured metacognitive calibration directly and found that participants showed poor resolution between confidence and actual accuracy when classifying

phishing emails, with confidence levels failing to reliably distinguish correct from incorrect classifications. Building on these findings, we predict that incorrect classifications will skew toward LIKELY and CERTAIN confidence levels rather than GUESSING, meaning participants will miss phishing emails while feeling sure of their classification. This overconfidence is expected to be strongest for pretexting, where a well-constructed pretext reads like a normal business email and no signal is available to produce appropriate uncertainty.

5. Dataset Design

5.1 Dataset Composition

The dataset is designed to contain 1,000 total cards: 690 phishing cards across six technique categories and 310 legitimate cards across three categories. This composition ensures sufficient phishing volume per technique category for statistical comparison while preventing participants from exploiting a coin-flip strategy. The 69/31 ratio does not mirror real enterprise email, where the overwhelming majority of messages are legitimate; it is chosen to make the base rate unintuitive and difficult to game. Because sessions draw 10 cards via uniform random selection from each participant's remaining pool without stratification, the phishing-to-legitimate mix varies from session to session. A given session might contain 8 phishing and 2 legitimate cards, or 5 and 5, or any other combination drawn from the pool-level ratio.

Table 1: Phishing Card Distribution (690 cards)

Technique	Easy (35)	Medium (35)	Hard (35)	Extreme (10)
Urgency	35	35	35	10
Authority Impersonation	35	35	35	10
Credential Harvest	35	35	35	10
Hyper-personalization	35	35	35	10
Pretexting	35	35	35	10
Fluent Prose	35	35	35	10

Table 2: Legitimate Card Distribution (310 cards)

Category	Description	Cards
Transactional	Receipts, shipping, account updates	110
Marketing	Newsletters, promotions, announcements	100
Workplace	Internal comms, HR, IT notices	100

5.2 Card Generation and Quality Control

All cards, both phishing and legitimate, are generated using large language models from the Anthropic Claude family. The generation pipeline supports multiple providers (Claude Haiku, Claude Sonnet, and OpenAI GPT-4o). The current dataset of 1,000 cards comprises 798 generated by Claude Haiku 4.5 and 202 by Claude Sonnet 4.6 (approximately 80/20). Both models receive the same structured prompt templates, but their differing generation characteristics produce natural variation in sentence structure, vocabulary, and tone. Each card's generating model is recorded in the database (ai_provider and ai_model fields), enabling post-hoc analysis of whether model choice affects participant detection rates. Cards are generated in batches per technique category and difficulty tier, with industry context randomized across 14 sectors to ensure contextual diversity.

Difficulty tier is operationalized through a concrete rubric applied at generation time via per-technique prompt specifications. The rubric defines four tiers: Easy cards contain one or more traditional tells (suspicious sender domain, explicit urgency language, implausible pretext, direct credential request); a single careful read should identify the phishing attempt. Medium cards present good surface quality with the technique present but subtle; detection requires attention to contextual inconsistencies rather than obvious red flags. Hard cards are high-quality phishing with the technique well-concealed within plausible correspondence; detection requires close reading and forensic inspection. Extreme cards are near-indistinguishable from legitimate email with the technique fully embedded; a security-aware reader may miss the attack on first and second pass. All four tiers are included in the Research Mode card pool. Expert Mode (Section 6.4) uses a separate set of exclusively extreme-tier cards that are not part of the Research Mode pool. Forensic metadata also varies by tier: easy and medium cards default to failed email authentication (SPF/DKIM/DMARC), while hard and extreme cards may present verified or ambiguous authentication status, removing header analysis as a reliable shortcut. Research Mode sessions draw 10 cards via uniform random selection from the full pool of unanswered cards without stratification by difficulty, producing a naturalistic and variable difficulty mix per session. Because detection difficulty is partly intrinsic to the technique itself, the same tier label does not imply identical absolute difficulty across categories. The primary analysis treats difficulty tier as a covariate to adjust for within-technique signal variation.

All generated cards enter an admin review pipeline prior to inclusion in the live dataset. A human reviewer evaluates each card for quality, internal consistency, and appropriate difficulty calibration. Cards failing review are rejected and do not enter the dataset. The dataset is frozen at version 1 upon reaching 1,000 approved cards. As a post-deployment quality control mechanism, the platform includes a card reporting feature. Participants can flag any card during classification, selecting from predefined issue categories and optionally providing a free-text comment. All reports are retained in the dataset regardless of outcome. A reported card is excluded from the primary analysis only if review confirms it meets one of three pre-registered criteria: (1) incorrect ground truth, where the card is labeled phishing but contains no phishing indicators or labeled legitimate but contains phishing elements; (2) internal inconsistency, where forensic metadata contradicts the email content (e.g., the body references a link but no URL is present, or authentication results do not match the card's intended configuration); or (3) rendering or display error, where the card fails to display correctly, truncating or hiding information the participant needs to classify it. Reports that do not meet any of these criteria (e.g., complaints about difficulty or perceived unfairness) do not result in exclusion. As a secondary screen, cards with observed accuracy falling more than two standard deviations below their technique-and-difficulty group mean will be manually inspected against the same three criteria, provided the card has been observed by at least five participants (cards with fewer observations are too sparse for reliable outlier detection). This screening step is an inspection trigger, not an exclusion mechanism: cards flagged by the screen are excluded only if inspection reveals an objective defect meeting the criteria above. Cards that are simply difficult survive inspection. Because this screen uses outcome data to identify inspection targets, the sensitivity analysis described in Section 7.1 reports results both with and without screened exclusions to confirm that outcome-informed inspection does not

materially alter the findings. Exclusion decisions from participant reports are made before examining per-card outcome data. The raw dataset will include all answers, with excluded cards flagged rather than deleted, enabling independent verification of all exclusion decisions.

5.3 Phishing Technique Taxonomy

The six phishing technique categories represent distinct social engineering mechanisms selected for their prevalence in threat intelligence reporting and their differing cognitive demands on the classifier. These categories are not mutually exclusive in practice: real-world phishing emails frequently combine multiple techniques (e.g., authority impersonation with urgency, pretexting with credential harvesting). The taxonomy captures the primary social engineering mechanism as specified by the generation prompt, not the exclusive mechanism present in the resulting email. If an authority-impersonation prompt produces an email that also contains urgency language, the card is classified under authority impersonation because that was the intended primary mechanism. This approach trades ecological purity for analytical clarity: it enables cleaner technique-level comparisons at the cost of some overlap between categories. Readers should interpret technique-level findings as reflecting the primary mechanism rather than a strict partition of phishing strategies.

Urgency. Emails manufacturing artificial time pressure to force fast, unconsidered decisions. These messages invoke expiring accounts, unprocessed payments, or looming security events. The detection challenge is structural: urgency also appears in legitimate transactional email (password resets, shipping alerts), making it difficult to isolate as a signal when all emails are well-written.

Authority Impersonation. Messages impersonating executives, IT departments, HR, legal teams, or established institutions. The attack exploits deference to authority figures. In the dataset, all sender names and organizations are plausible rather than obviously spoofed, removing the low-effort check of identifying misspelled brand names.

Credential Harvest. Classic credential phishing directing recipients to a login, verification, or account recovery flow. Cards present the message itself and reveal forensic signals (SPF/DKIM/DMARC, reply-to analysis, URL characteristics) after classification. Detection tests whether participants can identify phishing intent from message content and available forensic metadata (headers, URL characteristics, reply-to analysis) before the post-classification signal breakdown.

Hyper-personalization. Emails referencing contextually plausible personal or professional detail to establish authenticity. Cards use plausible contextual detail rather than detail drawn from the specific participant, which is a deliberate scope boundary. The study measures recognition of hyper-personalization as a technique structure, not the effectiveness of genuine personalization.

Pretexting. Multi-step social engineering establishing a believable backstory before making the ask. The email arrives as a continuation of an implied interaction. Detection requires recognizing the setup as artificial rather than evaluating the surface-level request.

Fluent Prose. Phishing with no urgency cues, no authority figure, no personalization, and no pretext. Polished, neutral business language making a routine business request (scheduling, sharing documents, confirming details). This category is not a residual bin for unclassifiable cards. Cards are assigned to Fluent Prose only when the generation prompt explicitly specifies the absence of all five named technique markers; cards that partially employ a named technique (e.g., mild urgency) are classified under the relevant technique category regardless of prose quality. The operational definition is generative: the prompt instructs the model to produce a phishing email that relies solely on plausibility and routine tone, with no social engineering mechanism beyond the request itself. Fluent Prose serves as the study's control condition for technique salience, measuring detection difficulty when no identifiable social engineering structure is present for a trained user to recognize. It also models the operational profile of AI-enabled

business email compromise (BEC), in which a well-crafted message requests a routine action with no identifiable trick.

6. Study Platform and Data Collection Methodology

6.1 Threat Terminal

Figure 1. Sessions draw 10 cards without replacement. Participants classify using forensic tools with telemetry at each decision. Research Mode caps at 30 answers; other modes use separate cards.

Threat Terminal is a purpose-built game-based research platform accessible at research.scottaltiparmak.com. Participants interact with a retro terminal interface in which they are presented with AI-generated emails one at a time. Each email is rendered with interactive forensic investigation tools available during classification: participants can reveal the actual sender address behind a display name, open email authentication headers (SPF/DKIM/DMARC), inspect the destination URL behind any hyperlink in the body, and review attachment metadata. For each email, participants make two decisions: a classification (phishing or legitimate) and a confidence level (GUESSING, LIKELY, or CERTAIN). Each decision earns experience points (XP) scaled by the correctness and confidence of the classification. Sessions target ten cards. After each completed session, participants receive a summary forensic breakdown reviewing the signals present in each card they classified. Because participants have access to forensic tools during classification, technique-level bypass rates reflect the combined difficulty of the technique and its metadata profile rather than the social engineering mechanism alone.

The platform requires account creation via email one-time password (no persistent password is stored). All participants begin in Research Mode, which contributes classified answers to the study dataset and is capped at 30 answers (three sessions of ten cards each). After completing Research Mode, participants unlock Freeplay mode, which uses separately generated cards that are not part of the research

card pool. Freeplay data is not persisted to the study database. Expert Mode, described in Section 6.4, also unlocks at this point.

6.2 Data Collected Per Answer

The platform records a comprehensive telemetry record per classified card, organized into six categories:

Identification. Answer UUID, session UUID (grouping answers into rounds), pseudonymous player UUID (not linked to email outside the authentication layer), card identifier, and game mode flag (Research Mode records only).

Card ground truth. Phishing status (boolean), technique label (one of the six phishing categories or three legitimate categories), difficulty tier, card source (a schema field supporting future dataset expansion; all cards in the current study are AI-generated), email authentication status (SPF/DKIM pass or fail), presence of Reply-To header, and presence of embedded URLs.

Classification response. Player answer (phishing or legitimate), correctness (boolean), confidence level (GUESSING, LIKELY, or CERTAIN), and answer input method (button click or keyboard shortcut).

Timing. Three timing measurements are captured in milliseconds: total time from card render to final answer submission, time from confidence selection to final answer, and confidence selection deliberation time (elapsed time before the participant selects a confidence level).

Forensic interaction telemetry. Scroll depth percentage (how far the participant scrolled through the email body), whether email headers were opened (boolean), and whether embedded URLs were inspected (boolean). These fields enable analysis of whether participants who engage forensic tools exhibit higher detection accuracy.

Session context. Answer ordinal position within the session, running correct-answer streak length, cumulative correct count at time of answer, daily challenge flag, dataset version, UTC timestamp, and self-reported professional background (optional; see Section 6.3).

6.3 Professional Background Self-Reporting

Participants may optionally self-report professional background on their account profile. This field enables group comparison analysis examining whether security experience predicts detection accuracy. Three categories are available: INFOSEC/CYBERSECURITY (working in security), TECHNICAL/NON-SECURITY (technical role outside security), and OTHER (general users, students, non-technical roles). Selecting a background category is optional; participants who decline to specify are excluded from group comparison analysis while their answer data remains in the main dataset.

6.4 Expert Mode

After submitting 30 research answers (three completed sessions), participants unlock Expert Mode. Expert Mode draws exclusively from separately generated extreme-tier cards (10 cards per technique, 60 cards total in the phishing pool) and awards double XP. These cards are not part of the Research Mode pool. Critically, Expert Mode answers are not included in the primary research dataset. Upon graduating to Expert Mode, participants can no longer contribute new data to the study; they continue to play for engagement and can review their personal statistics, but their subsequent classifications are excluded from analysis. This design prevents experienced participants from skewing the research dataset with repeated exposure effects. Expert Mode engagement data is tracked separately for potential secondary analysis of skill progression. A secondary consequence of this design is a form of informative censoring: the most engaged participants are capped at exactly 30 research observations, while less engaged participants contribute fewer. If engagement correlates with detection ability, the research dataset may underweight high-ability participants relative to their potential contribution. The random intercept partially accounts for

this by estimating per-participant ability, but it cannot fully correct for the truncated observation window on high-engagement individuals.

6.5 Forensic Signal Pedagogy

After each session, participants are shown a detailed breakdown of forensic signals for every card reviewed. Signals include: SPF/DKIM/DMARC authentication status, reply-to address mismatch detection, send timestamp analysis, URL inspector revealing destination addresses behind displayed anchor text, and attachment name analysis. This serves a dual purpose: it functions as the educational layer of the platform, and it trains participants on substantive detection signals rather than the linguistic quality signals that the study is designed to neutralize.

6.6 Ethical Considerations

The study involves classification tasks posing no more than minimal risk, collects no sensitive personally identifiable information in research tables, employs no deception, and does not involve vulnerable populations. Participants provide informed consent before entering Research Mode and may withdraw at any time. This study is conducted by an independent researcher without institutional affiliation. The Common Rule (45 CFR 46) applies to research conducted or supported by federal agencies or at institutions holding a Federal Wide Assurance; as neither condition applies here, formal IRB review was not required. The protocol was designed to meet the substantive ethical standards of the Common Rule's exempt-research criteria (Category 2: survey and behavioral research).

Informed consent is obtained prior to participation. Before entering Research Mode, participants are presented with a disclosure screen explaining: the purpose of the study, the nature of the task, exactly what data is recorded (answer, confidence level, response time, header and URL interaction behavior, session position, and self-reported background), and what is not recorded (email address, IP address, location, or any identifying information). Participants must acknowledge this disclosure before contributing research answers.

Data minimization is enforced at the architecture level. Email addresses are stored only in the authentication layer and are never joined to research data. Research answers are linked to a pseudonymous player UUID. Usernames are user-chosen and do not require real names. Professional background self-reporting is optional, with an explicit "prefer not to say" option. No participant can be re-identified from the research dataset alone. Platform-level controls mitigate common threats to data integrity: account creation requires email verification via one-time password, each email address can create only one Research Mode account, the 30-answer cap prevents disproportionate contribution, and answer-level telemetry enables post-hoc identification of bot-like or inattentive response patterns (e.g., sub-second classification times, zero scroll depth).

7. Participant Sampling and Recruitment

Participants are recruited through voluntary discovery of the Threat Terminal platform via the author's professional website, blog, social media channels, and presentations at cybersecurity community events including the South Florida ISSA chapter meetings and the Palm Beach State College Cybersecurity Symposium. Research Mode participation requires free account creation via email one-time password.

This is a recruited convenience sample. The implications of this sampling approach are discussed in Section 8.

7.1 Planned Statistical Analysis

The primary analysis will use mixed-effects logistic regression on phishing cards only, with classification correctness (correct/incorrect) as the binary dependent variable. Legitimate cards do not carry

technique labels and are excluded from this model. Answers associated with cards excluded through the reporting and review process described in Section 5.2 are removed from the primary analysis; a sensitivity analysis will re-run the primary model with all excluded cards included, and both sets of estimates will be reported. Phishing technique category, difficulty tier, and answer ordinal (position within the participant's sequence of classifications) will be specified as fixed effects. The model will include crossed random effects: a random intercept for participant to account for repeated measures within individuals, and a random intercept for card to account for intrinsic item-level difficulty variation (this intercept also absorbs variance from any undetected item-level defects). Two covariates address within-study learning: answer ordinal captures gradual improvement, and session number (1, 2, or 3) captures discrete learning at session boundaries when participants receive forensic signal breakdowns. If the card random effect cannot be estimated reliably due to sparse per-card observation counts, both models (with and without the card intercept) will be reported.

Technique-level bypass rates will be reported as the proportion of phishing cards incorrectly classified as legitimate within each technique category, with 95% confidence intervals. Pairwise comparisons between techniques will use Bonferroni-corrected post-hoc tests to control the family-wise error rate across the 15 pairwise comparisons. Signal detection metrics (d-prime and criterion c) will be computed using both phishing and legitimate card classifications to separate detection sensitivity from response bias. Because the dataset contains 69% phishing cards, participants may develop a base-rate-driven tendency to classify ambiguous emails as phishing; d-prime isolates discriminability from this bias, and criterion c quantifies the bias directly. These metrics will be reported alongside raw bypass rates for all primary analyses.

Group comparisons (H2) will extend the model by adding self-reported professional background as a fixed effect. The technique-by-background interaction will also be tested to explore whether the security professional advantage is uniform or concentrated in specific technique categories; with 100 participants divided across three background categories, this interaction analysis is exploratory and may be underpowered. Confidence calibration analysis (H3) will plot the proportion of correct classifications at each confidence level (GUESSING, LIKELY, CERTAIN) and use ordinal regression to model confidence level as a function of classification correctness, with technique category as a covariate. The three-level confidence scale is coarser than instruments typically used in calibration research, so findings should be interpreted as detecting gross overconfidence rather than providing fine-grained calibration measurement. Secondary analyses may examine whether forensic tool engagement and classification timing predict detection accuracy, leveraging the telemetry fields described in Section 6.2. These analyses are not pre-registered and will be reported as exploratory.

With 100 participants each contributing up to 30 research answers, the dataset would contain approximately 3,000 classified cards, of which roughly 2,070 would be phishing (69% base rate), yielding approximately 345 phishing classifications per technique category. A two-proportion power analysis at $\alpha = 0.05$ indicates that 345 observations per group provides 91% power to detect a 10 percentage point difference in bypass rates between any two techniques, and 80% power requires a minimum of approximately 72 participants. These estimates assume independent observations; the mixed-effects model's random intercept reduces the effective sample size, so these figures should be interpreted as approximate upper bounds. Pilot data shows meaningful between-participant variance in accuracy ($SD = 0.23$), confirming that the random intercept is warranted. Initial pilot data shows variable participation depth: of 70 early participants, 17 completed the full 30-card research allotment (24%), 47 completed at least one full 10-card session (67%), and 41 contributed 10 or fewer classifications. Partial sessions are included because the mixed-effects model handles unbalanced data natively. Because cards are drawn without replacement via uniform random selection, per-participant technique exposure is unbalanced; the mixed-effects model accommodates this structure. There is no minimum answer requirement per participant. The target recruitment minimum is 100 Research Mode participants.

7.2 Initial Pilot Data

The following initial pilot data is included solely to demonstrate that the platform is functional, that data collection is proceeding as designed, and that the telemetry pipeline produces usable records. These numbers should not be interpreted as statistically powered results. As of March 2026, 70 participants have contributed 996 classified cards in Research Mode. Participation depth varies considerably: 17 participants completed the full 30-card research allotment (24%), 47 completed at least one full 10-card session (67%), while 41 contributed 10 or fewer classifications. This variation is common in voluntary online studies. Each classification response is retained as an observation; the analysis explicitly models within-participant dependence through the random intercept described in Section 7.1, so partial sessions do not require exclusion.

In the pilot sample, aggregate detection accuracy across all 996 classified cards was 86.2%. Mean confidence on correct classifications was 2.72 compared to 2.31 on incorrect classifications (scale: 1 = GUESSING, 2 = LIKELY, 3 = CERTAIN). Mean time to classify was 58.0 seconds per card. Of the 70 participants, 31 self-reported as INFOSEC/CYBERSECURITY, 12 as TECHNICAL/NON-SECURITY, 20 as OTHER, and 5 preferred not to say. These descriptive statistics confirm that the platform is recording the intended data fields with plausible values; no inferential analysis is conducted on this pilot sample.

At the technique level, pilot bypass rates ranged from 9.9% (credential harvest) to 20.7% (fluent prose). These directional patterns are noted solely to confirm that the platform is producing variance across technique categories as designed; no inferential conclusions are drawn from this pilot sample. The empirical findings paper will be submitted as a separate publication upon reaching the target minimum of 100 Research Mode participants, providing the statistical power described in Section 7.1.

8. Limitations

8.1 Self-Selected Sample

Participants are recruited through a combination of personal networks, word-of-mouth referrals, social media outreach, and professional community sharing. Recruitment deliberately targets both security professionals and non-security individuals (friends, family, colleagues outside the field) to broaden the sample beyond the security-engaged population that would self-select into a phishing research platform organically. Despite this effort, the sample remains a convenience sample: participants must choose to visit the platform, create a Research Mode account, and complete at least one session. This process likely still over-represents people with above-average security awareness or interest relative to a true general workforce sample. Findings should be interpreted as measuring classification performance within the Threat Terminal environment by a recruited convenience sample with mixed professional backgrounds, rather than as estimates of real-world phishing detection rates in a general workforce. The self-reported professional background variable (Section 6.3) allows post-hoc comparison across subgroups, but it does not substitute for probability sampling.

8.2 Game Context

Participants know they are classifying emails in a game environment. This produces different cognitive engagement than real-world email triage, where classification competes with other tasks and attention is not guaranteed. Game context likely inflates detection rates by focusing participant attention exclusively on the classification task, removing the competing demands of normal workload. Combined with forensic tool access, instructional feedback between sessions, and the self-selected sample, the study environment is closer to a structured assessment of phishing recognition skill than to naturalistic email triage. Absolute detection rates from this study should not be compared directly to workplace phishing simulation click rates, which measure a fundamentally different construct.

8.3 AI-Generated Stimuli

All cards, including legitimate ones, are AI-generated. This partially standardizes linguistic quality across conditions but means the legitimate emails do not carry the full contextual richness of real correspondence. In practice, recipient-specific context (knowing the sender, expecting the email, recognizing internal references) is a strong legitimacy signal that the dataset cannot replicate. Detection rates for legitimate emails in this study should not be read as reflecting real-world false positive rates. Because all stimuli share high linguistic quality, the Fluent Prose category (defined by the absence of named technique markers) partially overlaps with the quality baseline shared by all conditions. As described in Section 5.3, Fluent Prose is structurally asymmetric with the five named techniques, and its bypass rate measures detection difficulty at the floor of technique salience rather than serving as a direct peer comparison.

8.4 Hyper-Personalization Ceiling

As noted in Section 5.3, hyper-personalization cards use plausible contextual detail rather than genuine information about the specific participant. This is a deliberate scope boundary: the study measures recognition of hyper-personalization as a technique structure, not the effectiveness of genuine personalization. In-study bypass rates for this technique will not reflect its real-world ceiling and should be interpreted accordingly.

8.5 Self-Reported Background

Professional background is self-reported and not independently verified. Participants may misclassify their background or select options that do not accurately reflect their day-to-day exposure to security concepts. Group comparisons should be treated as approximate.

8.6 Card Classification Reliability

Each card in the dataset is assigned a technique label and difficulty tier by the author alone. No second coder independently classified the cards, and no inter-rater reliability metric (e.g., Cohen's kappa) is reported. This is a limitation. The risk is that borderline cards may be assigned to technique categories inconsistently, particularly between adjacent categories such as authority impersonation and pretexting. Two design features partially mitigate this concern. First, technique assignment is not a post-hoc judgment: it is determined at generation time by the prompt specification, which explicitly names the technique and its structural requirements. The card's category is an input to generation, not an inference from the output. Second, the admin review pipeline rejects cards whose content does not clearly instantiate the specified technique. Nonetheless, a formal reliability audit with an independent coder is planned prior to publication of the empirical findings paper, and the dataset release will include the generation prompts to enable independent verification of category assignments.

8.7 Within-Study Learning Effects

Participants receive forensic signal breakdowns after each 10-card session, meaning classification decisions in sessions two and three are informed by feedback from prior sessions. This pedagogical feedback is integral to the platform's design but introduces a potential learning confound: later sessions may show improved accuracy independent of technique or difficulty. The planned analysis will include session order as a covariate in the mixed-effects model to estimate the magnitude of within-study learning. If significant session-order effects are observed, session-adjusted bypass rates will be reported alongside raw rates. A further possibility is that learning effects vary by technique: participants may quickly learn to recognize credential harvest attempts while showing little improvement on fluent prose or pretexting. If pilot data or initial results suggest differential learning, a technique-by-ordinal interaction term will be tested in the model, though this increases model complexity and may be underpowered at the target sample size. This learning trajectory is also a secondary research output of independent interest.

8.8 Base Rate Awareness

As described in Section 5.1, the 69/31 phishing-to-legitimate ratio is a design choice to ensure statistical power and prevent gaming, not a reflection of real-world base rates. In real enterprise email, the overwhelming majority of messages are legitimate. Because each participant draws only 30 cards (three 10-card sessions) from the pool without stratification, individual participants may experience session-level ratios that deviate substantially from the pool-level 69/31 split. Absolute detection rates should therefore be interpreted in context rather than as estimates of real-world performance, and the planned analysis will report signal detection metrics (d-prime, criterion) alongside raw accuracy to separate discriminability from response bias.

8.9 Single-Family Generation

The dataset comprises 798 cards generated by Claude Haiku 4.5 and 202 by Claude Sonnet 4.6. While using two models from the same family introduces stylistic variation, both share underlying training characteristics, and phishing and legitimate cards may exhibit stylistic similarities that would not exist in real-world email. In practice, phishing and legitimate emails originate from different authors with different writing profiles, and stylistic variation between sources may itself serve as a detection signal. The generation pipeline supports additional providers (including OpenAI GPT-4o), and future dataset versions may incorporate multi-family generation to further diversify the stimulus pool. Per-card model provenance is recorded in the dataset, enabling secondary analysis of whether generation model affects detection rates. Findings from the current dataset should be interpreted as applicable to AI-quality, partially standardized conditions rather than as reflecting detection performance against the full diversity of real-world phishing.

9. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presents the study protocol, dataset design, and methodological framework for an experiment on human phishing detection in which all stimuli are AI-generated at consistent linguistic quality. As LLM technology erodes the reliability of linguistic quality as a phishing detection signal, the empirical research base on which security awareness training is built requires updating. This study is designed to produce technique-level detection data within an AI-quality platform environment. While the study context differs from real-world email triage, the relative ordering of technique difficulty and the patterns of overconfidence observed may inform how practitioners, trainers, and researchers approach the AI-phishing transition.

The Threat Terminal platform enables scalable data collection outside laboratory settings while maintaining data quality through pseudonymization, admin review of stimuli, and separation of freeplay from research data. Hypotheses are stated prior to full analysis to distinguish predictions from post-hoc rationalizations. Initial pilot data from 70 participants confirms that the platform is functional and the data collection pipeline is producing usable records.

A subsequent empirical paper will report technique-level bypass rates, group differences by professional background, confidence-accuracy analysis, and practical implications for security awareness training design once the target sample of 100 participants has been reached. Researchers interested in collaborating, reviewing the methodology, or accessing the dataset upon completion are invited to contact the author.

Upon publication of the empirical findings, the following materials will be released alongside the dataset: the structured prompt framework used for card generation, the technique taxonomy and difficulty tier codebook, the full exclusion criteria and review log, and a schema summary of all telemetry fields collected per classification.

Addendum: Protocol Revision v1.1 (March 22, 2026)

This addendum documents a methodological revision implemented during active data collection and is appended to the original protocol to maintain transparency. The original protocol text above is unmodified.

A.1 Summary of Change

Effective March 22, 2026, the email authentication header inspection panel was removed from the Threat Terminal platform interface. Participants enrolled after this date classify emails based on visible email content (sender address, subject line, body text, embedded URLs, and attachment metadata) without access to SPF/DKIM/DMARC authentication status or Reply-To header metadata. The dataset card pool, card content, difficulty assignments, and all other study parameters remain unchanged.

A.2 Rationale

Post-hoc analysis of the first 105 participants (1,716 classified cards) revealed that email authentication status was confounded with difficulty tier in the card dataset. As described in Section 5.2 of the original protocol, easy and medium phishing cards default to failed authentication, while hard and extreme cards present verified or ambiguous authentication. Legitimate emails present verified authentication in 97.1% of cases, with no legitimate email presenting failed authentication. This distribution created a condition in which a participant who inspected headers could use authentication status as a near-deterministic classifier for easy and medium phishing cards without evaluating email content.

Behavioral telemetry confirmed that this confound was not merely theoretical. Of the 105 participants, 38.1% opened headers on every card classified, 39.0% opened headers on some cards, and 22.9% never opened headers. Participants who always opened headers achieved 91.6% overall accuracy compared to 72.7% for participants who never opened headers. On medium-difficulty phishing cards (where authentication status was uniformly “fail”), participants who always opened headers achieved 96.0% accuracy compared to 76.2% for non-openers, a gap of 19.8 percentage points. On fail-authentication phishing emails specifically, opening headers was associated with 92.0% accuracy compared to 74.1% for those who did not, an 18-point difference.

A secondary consideration was participant comprehension. The study recruits participants across a range of professional backgrounds, including individuals with no formal security training. Anecdotal observation during early data collection suggested that participants unfamiliar with email authentication concepts were confused or misled by the authentication status indicators, interpreting them inconsistently rather than as the forensic signal they were intended to represent. While this observation was not formally measured, it reinforced the decision to remove a feature that appeared to introduce interpretive noise for a substantial portion of the participant pool.

Because the primary research question concerns which phishing techniques produce the lowest human detection rates based on email content and social engineering structure, the availability of authentication metadata as a shortcut undermined the construct validity of the measurement. Removing the header panel isolates technique as the independent variable, which was the original research objective.

A.3 Impact on Data Collection and Analysis

The study data is partitioned into two phases using an `auth_visible` boolean field recorded on every answer row. Phase 1 (`auth_visible = true`) comprises all responses collected before the revision, during which participants had access to the header inspection panel. Phase 2 (`auth_visible = false`) comprises all responses collected after the revision, during which the header panel was not available. Both phases use the same locked card dataset (v1, 1,000 cards).

The empirical findings paper will report Phase 1 and Phase 2 results separately and in aggregate. For the primary analysis of technique-level detection rates, Phase 2 data provides the cleanest measurement of the

intended construct. Phase 1 data remains valid for secondary analyses, including: (1) the effect of metadata availability on detection accuracy, (2) the interaction between header inspection behavior and technique-level performance, and (3) the comparison of detection accuracy with and without forensic tools. The `headers_opened` telemetry field continues to be recorded in Phase 2 (expected value: false for all rows) to maintain schema consistency across phases.

A.4 Scope of Revision

This revision affects only the platform interface. No changes were made to the card dataset, difficulty tier assignments, technique taxonomy, scoring system, consent framework, or any other element of the study protocol. Participants enrolled after the revision date are informed of the same study parameters described in the original consent disclosure, with the exception that the header inspection tool is no longer referenced as an available forensic tool. All hypotheses stated in Section 4 of the original protocol remain unchanged.

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